

Relationship of Job Satisfaction to Well-Being- The Government-Owned Enterprise as an Example

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Abstract

There is an obvious difference of the operation between state-run businesses and privately owned enterprise. The fact is that state-run businesses are often in a dilemma while they are planning to make profits because they have to take both regulation and the public benefits into consideration. The purpose of the study is to investigate state-run employees' job satisfaction and well-being in Miao-Li country of Taiwan Power Company. The study was conducted by questionnaire. The 222 valid samples were selected from 260 ones. Research results are concluded as follows:

There is a significant difference between employees' background factors and their "Job Achievement" dimension of job satisfaction such as status of marriage, educational backgrounds, ages and working seniority. The employees' with different genders and job types has a significant difference on "Promotion Opportunity" dimension of job satisfaction. The employees with various job types have a significant difference on "Job Support" dimension of job satisfaction. There is a significant difference on employees' job types for "Mental Physical and Health" dimension of well-being. There is a significant difference on employees' working seniority for "Life satisfaction" dimension of job satisfaction. The degree of job satisfaction and well-being has positive correlation. The dimensions of "Job Achievement" and "Colleague Relationship" have significant difference on the employees' well-being. There are some findings and suggestions provided to related departments and government as refines for management and applications.

Keywords: Government-owned enterprise's employees; Job satisfaction; Well-being.

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Government-owned enterprises are running business with the same business models as any other private enterprises, except for only one difference that the government-owned enterprises are usually caught in the dilemma of enterprise profits and public interests as well as laws and regulations. Taiwan Power Company (TPC), in pursuit of safe and stable power supplies, demands personnel with specific professional backgrounds and capability of stand-by for emergency contingency, hence less HR replacement options. Due to the rising material prices and the long-lasting political issues, TPC has run into consecutive losses for years. Therefore, raising electricity rates seems an inevitable decision to make and TPC employees will still do their best in their positions despite of all the public criticism.

Job has been one of the important sources for personal sense of accomplishment as well as overall life perspective. The state of well-being accounts for the subjective assessment on the degree of one's overall satisfaction to his personal life in current status, as well as the important index of personal quality of living (Yang, 1980). Nowadays, the enterprises should emphasize on the pursuit of employees' well-being as business goal and profit tool by balancing their works and life. However, due to national security concerns for power supply as a monopoly industry, there is an urge for studies on

relationship of job satisfactions to the well-being of TPC employees.

1.2 Research Motive and Purpose

Since TPC employees are always in stand-by status and in positions of cooperating with national policies, their personal job satisfactions certainly affect their working efficiencies and subsequently the enterprise's success. Therefore, TPC employees' job satisfactions had become one of the research motivations. The current society in Taiwan has been in a transition state, in which the population structure is aging with more elderly yet less youths. TPC employees in their middle ages happen to part of the ones with the most burdens in the society. The study on their senses of well-being in such rough times had given this research a second motivation. Employees' well-being and healthiness are as important indexes and values as enterprise's productivity and performance. However, there have been barely few studies about the relationship of job satisfaction to well-being even though many were related to the subjects of job satisfaction and well-being individually. The relationship of TPC employees' job satisfaction to their well-being was the third motivation for this study. In summary, the study was aimed for the goals as follows:

- i) To analyze if there are any variations in job satisfactions of the government-owned enterprise's employees with different population variables.**
- ii) To analyze if there are any variations in well-being of the government-owned enterprise's employees with different population variables.**
- iii) To analyze if there is any positive impact of the government-owned enterprise's employees job satisfactions to their well-being.**
- iv) Well-being prediction with degrees of job satisfaction.**

2. Literature Review

2.1 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to the worker's attitude toward his job and workplace. According to Hoppock (1935), job satisfaction, as the worker's subjective response to his job, accounted for the worker's psychological and physical satisfactions to his environmental factors. Wexley & Yukl (1977) indicated that the comprehensions of employees' expected workplaces and their actual ones helped to define their job satisfactions; whereas expected workplaces might be related to personal requirements, values, characteristics, contemporary social comparisons, former working experiences and reference groups, while actual workplaces might be determined by compensations, payments, management system, partners, job safety and promotion channels.

According to Chou (2003), job satisfaction implied one's positive and delighted state of mind when evaluating his job or working experiences. The occurrence of positive emotions would be identified as job satisfaction, otherwise job dissatisfaction. The higher job satisfaction, the more positive attitudes and subsequently more positive personal behaviors would be; even though one's behaviors might still have to compromise to other factors. One's subjective emotional responses and attitudes toward his job would be determined by his overall emotional orientation toward his current job at all the related levels; whereas positive orientation implying job satisfaction, otherwise job dissatisfaction.

Tsai (2006) indicated that there would be an urge for new dimensions of evaluating employees' job satisfactions in domestic enterprises, since job satisfaction was composed of many dimensions such as job achievement, compensations, directors' recognitions, colleagues' relationships and promotion opportunities rather than merely one single dimension.

2.2 Well-Being

According to Argyle (1987), well-being, referred to the positive psychological state of mind, should be deemed as life satisfaction as well as degrees of positive and negative emotions. Such definition had integrated the overall cognitions of happiness and emotional aspects. Moreover, one incident might trigger one's personal emotions and subsequently affect his perspective of life through the process of self-identification and personal characteristics. The state of well-being might be a subjective feeling of self-cognition upon accomplishment of certain goals, which could be evaluated with personal perceptions based on his own characteristics.

Ryff (1989) indicated that the state of well-being should be not only happiness, but also self-realizations of potentials and perfections. The state of well-being, based on perfect theory, tended to examine the feelings of growth and maturity upon experiences of life challenges. Keyes (1998) had proposed with the concept of "Social Well-being" referring to social challenges including social acceptance, social contribution, social realization, social cohesion and social integration.

There are many nouns representing the concept as the state of well-being including: happiness, satisfaction, well-being, subjective well-being and psychological well-being. According to Lu (1998), assessment on quality of living should be composed of positive emotions and subjective perspectives toward overall life satisfactions. According to the definition

of subjective well-being, it should be considered as a long-term and stable state of well-being rather than a bunch of emotional reactions. In other words, Subjective well-being is a collective mental experience derived from perceptions and affections. The state of well-being as well-being is consisted of pure happiness yet not limited to it only. The true state of well-being involves with more diversities of factors and dimensions, ranging from personal emotions, recognitions, characteristics, life satisfactions, psychological happiness and social well-being; whereas subjective well-being accounts for the overall satisfactions.

3. Research Method

3.1 Research Framework

The research structure, based on the research purposes and the findings derived from the reference articles, was composed of population variables, job satisfaction variables and well-being variables as follows in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Research Framework

3.2 Research Hypothesis

The study was aimed to study the relationship of job satisfactions to well-being and their interactions. Based on the research structure, the questions and the corresponding hypothesis were proposed as follows:

H1: There would be significant variations in job satisfactions of the government-owned enterprise's employees with different population variables.

H2: There would be significant variations in well-being of the government-owned enterprise's employees with different population variables.

H3: There would be positive impacts of job satisfactions to well-being.

4. Empirical Study

4.1 Demographics of Sample

The study had conducted a survey of 260 copies of questionnaires, whereas 222 valid respondents were analyzed except for the 10 invalid ones with a response rate of 85 %. In terms of gender, the male respondents were with a dominant percentage of 86.9%, while 13.1% for the female ones. In aspect of marriage status, the married accounted the majority of 76.6%, while the unmarried of 23.4%. In terms of ages, the employees aged 41~50 year accounted for the most as 35.6%, followed by the ones aged 31~40 year as 28.8% and those aged 51~60 year as 23%; whereas the employees aged over 51 year accounted for 27%, therefore, it may be concluded that the job security and stability of TPC have given itself an ageing of HR structure. In aspect of education, the percentages of high school graduates, college graduates and university graduates were 27.9%, 30.2% and 30.6% accordingly plus 11.3% with Master graduate studies. In terms of service years, the employees with more than 21 years of services accounted for the most as 43.2%, followed by the ones with 6~10 years of services as 16.7% and those with less than 5 years of services as 14.9%, and finally the ones with 11~15 years and 16~20 years of services accounted for 12.6% each individually. The findings had indicated that there was an ageing problem in the HR structure of TPC (See Table 1).

DEMOGRAPHIC	ITEMS	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Gender	male	193	86.9%
	female	29	13.1%
Marriage status	married	170	76.6%
	unmarried	52	23.4%
Age status	less than 30	19	8.6%
	31-40	64	28.8%
	41-50	79	35.6%
	51-60	51	23.0%
	over 61	9	4.0%
Education status	high school	62	27.9%
	college	67	30.2%
	university	68	30.6%
	over Master	25	11.3%
Service years	less than 5 year	33	14.9%
	6-10	37	16.7%
	11-15	28	12.6%
	16-20	28	12.6%
	Over 21	96	43.2%

4.2 Job Satisfaction Variance Analysis

i) Gender Status

On gender status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for “Promotion Opportunities” dimension. According to t-test analysis, the female employees tended to have a higher degree of satisfaction for “Promotion Opportunity” than the male ones (See Table 2).

Table 2: Gender Status T Test Analysis for “Promotion Opportunity” Dimension of Job Satisfaction

Dimension	Gender Status	Average	T	p- Value
Promotion Opportunity	male	2.95	-2.775	0.008**
	female	3.44		

*p<0.05, **p<0.01 ***p<0.001

ii) Marriage Status

On marriage status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for “Job Achievement” dimension. According to t-test analysis, the married employees tended to have a higher degree of satisfaction for “Job Achievement” dimension than the unmarried ones (See Table 3).

Table 3: Marriage status t test analysis for “Job Achievement” dimension of job satisfaction

Dimension	Marriage Status	Average	T	p- Value
Job Achievement	unmarried	3.03	-3.652	0.000***
	married	3.48		

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001

iii) Education Status

On education status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for “Job Achievement” and “Job Support” dimensions. According to the posterior comparison analysis, the employees with high school educations tended to have a higher degree of satisfaction for “Job Achievement” dimension than the ones with university educations; while no significant variances for “Job Support” (See Table 4).

Table 4: Education Status ANOVA Analysis for “Job Achievement” Dimension of Job Satisfaction

Dimension	Education status	F	p- value	Scheffe
Job Support	(1) higher school	4.310	0.006**	(1)>(3)
	(2) college			
	(3) university			
	(4) over Master			

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001

iv) Age Status

On age status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for "Job Achievement" dimension. According to the posterior comparisons, the employees aged 51-60 year tended to have a higher degree of satisfaction for "Job Achievement" dimension than the ones aged 31-40 year (See Table 5).

Table 5: Age Status ANOVA Analysis for "Job Achievement" Dimension of Job Satisfaction				
Dimension	Age status	F	p- value	Scheffe
Job Achievement	(1) less than 30	3.642	0.007**	(4) > (2)
	(2) 31-40			
	(3) 41-50			
	(4) 51-60			
	(5) Over 61			

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

v) Service Year Status

On service year status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for "Job Achievement" and "Colleague Relationship" dimensions. According to the posterior comparisons analysis, the employees with more than 21 years of services tended to have a higher degree of satisfaction for "Job Achievement" dimension than the ones with less than 5 years of services; while no significant variances for "Colleague Relationship" according to the posterior comparisons analysis (See Table 6).

Table 6: Service Year Status ANOVA Analysis for "Job Achievement" Dimension of Job Satisfaction				
Dimension	Service year status	F	p- value	Scheffe
Job Achievement	(1) less than 5	4.057	0.003**	(5) > (1)
	(2) 6-10			
	(3) 11-15			
	(4) 16-20			
	(5) Over 21			

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

4.3 Well-Being Variance Analysis

i) Gender Status

On gender status discovered the p-values in the dimensions of "Life Satisfaction", "Social Relationship", "Positive Emotion", "Mental and Physical Health" were greater than 0.05 as below significance level.

ii) Marriage Status

On marriage status discovered the p-values in the dimensions of "Life Satisfaction", "Social Relationship", "Positive Emotion", "Mental and Physical Health" were greater than 0.05 as below significance level.

iii) Education Status

On education status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for “Life Satisfaction” and “Mental and Physical Health”; however, there were no significant variations in “Life Satisfaction” and “Mental and Physical Health” according to the posterior comparisons test method.

iv) Age Status

On age status discovered the p-values in the dimensions of “Life Satisfaction”, “Social Relationship”, “Positive Emotion”, “Mental and Physical Health” were greater than 0.05 as below significance level.

v) Service Year Status

On service year status discovered no significant variances in other dimensions except for “Life Satisfaction”. According to the posterior comparisons analysis, the employees with 11-15 years of services and the ones with more than 12 years of services tended to have higher degrees of satisfactions than those with less than 5 years of services (See Table 7).

Table 7: Service Year Status ANOVA Analysis for “Life Satisfaction” Dimension of Well-Being				
Dimension	Service year status	F	p- value	Scheffe
Life Satisfaction	(1) less than 5	3.623	0.007**	(3)>(1)
	(2) 6-10			
	(3) 11-15			(5)>(1)
	(4) 16-20			
	(5) Over 21			

*p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001

4.4 Correlation Analysis

This study employed Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis for the study of relationships between job satisfaction and well-being. The findings had indicated that the Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient of 0.614 had reached the significance level with a significant positive correlation (See Table 8).

Table 8: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of Job Satisfaction and Well-Being			
Variables		Job satisfaction	Well-being
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	0.614**
	Sig. (Two-tailed)		0.000
Well-being	Pearson Correlation	0.614**	1
	Sig. (Two-tailed)	0.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (Two-tailed)

4.5 Regression Analysis

The multiple correlation coefficient for the six dimensions of “Job Achievement”, “Salary and Welfare”, “ Leadership”, ”Job Support”, “Colleague Relationship” and “Promotion Opportunities” and the criterion variable of “Well-being” was 0.709; whereas the squared multiple correlation coefficient was 0.503. Both had indicated that the six dimensions accounted for 50.3% variance of the variable of “Well-being”. Since the standard regression coefficients of the six dimensions were all positive figures, it also indicated that all of the six dimensions had positive impacts on the criterion variable of “Well-being”. In the regression model, the two dimension of “Job Achievement” and “Colleague Relationship” tended to have significant predictive powers on the criterion variable of “Well-being”; whereas, the

regression coefficients of the dimension of “Salary and Welfare”, “Leadership”, “Job Support” and “Promotion Opportunities” below significance level indicated that these variables tended to have rather minor predictive powers on the criterion variable of “Well-being” (See Table 9).

$$Y \text{ (Well-being)} = 1.607 + 0.191 \text{ (Job Achievement)} + 0.065 \text{ (Salary and Welfare)} + 0.009 \text{ (Leadership)} + 0.072 \text{ (Job Support)} + 0.481 \text{ (Colleague Relationship)} + 0.063 \text{ (Promotion Opportunities)}$$

Table 9: Regression Analysis of Job Satisfaction to Well-Being

Dimension	B	Std. error	Beta (β)	t	p- values
Constant	1.607	3.147		10.214	0.000
Job Achievement	0.119	0.876	0.191	2.724	0.007**
Salary and Welfare	0.038	0.883	0.065	0.855	0.393
Leadership	0.005	0.749	0.009	0.128	0.898
Job Support	0.052	1.143	0.072	0.903	0.368
Colleague Relationship	0.365	0.908	0.481	8.041	0.000***
Promotion Opportunities	0.030	0.596	0.063	0.997	0.320

$R = 0.709$ $R^2 = 0.503$ Adjusted $R^2 = 0.489$

5. Conclusions and Suggestion

5.1 Conclusions

According to the questionnaire analysis, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of job satisfaction and well-being exceeding the significance level indicated that there existed a positive correlation between job satisfaction and well-being. Furthermore, the correlation coefficients for the dimensions of “Job Achievement”, “Salary and Welfare”, “Leadership”, “Job Support”, “Colleague Relationship” and “Promotion Opportunities” in aspect of job satisfaction and the dimensions of “Life Satisfaction”, “Social Relationship”, “Positive Emotion” and “Mental and Physical Health” all reached to the significance level. Therefore, it was concluded that there existed intensive relations between the dimensions for job satisfaction and those for well-being.

The two dimensions of “Job Achievement” and “Colleague Relationship” tended to have the optimal predictive powers on overall well-being; that is to say, the employees with higher “Job Achievement” tended to have better “Colleague Relationship” and higher senses of well-being. According to job satisfaction analysis, job stability and security provided the senior employees with higher senses of Job Achievement; whereas the senior ones accounting for 1/4 of the total tested populations had also revealed the ageing problem in the HR structure. Since there were only 8.6%, less than 1/10, of the total personnel below 30 years old, the taskforce allocation and job skills passing-on would certainly encounter a talent gap crisis. By observing the means of the different dimensions, it indicated that the means of the dimensions of “Job Achievement”, “Salary and Welfare” and “Promotion Opportunities” for the employees with less than 5 years of services were all less than 3; whereas they also had the lowest mean in the dimension of “Job Support” among the entire personnel population.

5.2 Suggestion

It is hoped that the findings and conclusions of this study may be applied as future references for the competent authority’s stipulation of regulations governing personnel allocation and other rules for the optimization of job efficiency and employees’ well-being.

- i) Due to the ageing problem in HR structure of TPC, an exit mechanism for employee retirement is highly recommended. Furthermore, since that the employees had rather poor satisfactions to the current promotion system and audit regulations, the competent authority should clarify the regulations of promotion and audit system to reduce the doubts of the employees in the future.
- ii) Junior employees tended to have lower degrees of satisfactions and senses of well-being; therefore, the competent authority needs to reinforce on the on-site pre-trainings of the new employees, as well as advanced on-job

trainings for talent cultivation. Furthermore, incentive policy is also recommended for the senior employees' passing on their skills and valuable experiences to prevent from talent gaps.

- iii) According to the data analysis, the younger junior employees tended to have lower degrees of job satisfactions and senses of well-being. The major causes could be the junior employees' lack of practical experiences and colleague relationship. Therefore, for the enhancement of practical experiences, it is suggested to invite the senior staff for more skill pass-on and experience sharing with the junior staff for the cultivation of professional abilities; however it may take relatively longer period of time due to the occupational features. It is hoped that the junior employees may gain higher degree of job satisfaction with more professional job skills; as well as more senses of well-being with higher self-cognition and colleague interactions.

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